

A High-precision and Low-complexity Framework for Calibration of Stand-alone Merging Units

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Abstract— A novel technique is presented for the synchronization of sampled value (SV) streams generated according to the IEC 61869-9 and IEC 61850-9-2 standards by devices aligned via the Precision Time Protocol (PTP), with measurement data obtained from reference instruments that do not support PTP. The proposed solution, in conjunction with a pre-characterized sampling digital multimeter (DMM), enables automated calibration of stand-alone merging units (SAMUs). A thorough characterization of the phase error of the DMM across all voltage and current ranges in sampling mode is also reported.

Index Terms—IEC 61850, measurement, merging unit, sampling, smart grids.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE transition toward digital substations, driven by the IEC 61850 standard, has revolutionized power system automation by enabling seamless interoperability and standardized communication protocols. Central to this framework is the stand-alone merging unit, a critical device responsible for digitizing analog current and voltage signals from instrument transformers and transmitting them as SVs over Ethernet networks. These SVs, governed by the requirements of standards IEC 61869-9 [1] and IEC 61850-9-2 [2], form the backbone of protection, control, and monitoring systems, where timing fidelity, synchronization, and measurement accuracy are paramount. Despite the widespread adoption of SAMUs, ensuring their metrological performance remains a significant challenge. Calibration of such equipment is essential to guarantee compliance with the standard IEC 61869-13 [3] and to maintain the integrity of time-synchronized data streams in dynamic grid environments.

Synchronization of stand-alone merging units is crucial to ensure accurate time alignment of the SVs. This is commonly achieved using the Precision Time Protocol, although some SAMUs also support synchronization via a pulse-per-second (PPS) signal. Achieving precise synchronization between PTP/PPS-enabled equipment under test and reference measurement systems operated in calibration laboratories presents a significant technical challenge.

Calibration facilities for SAMUs, as reported by National Metrology Institutes (NMIs), typically rely on digitizers that depend on hardware-based synchronization with the devices

under test aligned via PTP/PPS signals. These digitizers, which generally have a maximum full-scale range of ± 10 V, necessitate additional voltage and current transducers to accommodate the measurement ranges encountered during SAMU calibration. This requirement hinders the automation of the calibration process.

In [4], a timing board was used to synchronize the ± 10 V input reference digitizer, with the highest measured voltage of 70 V achieved using an external voltage divider. The same measurement system, equipped with an external 10 A shunt, was employed to characterize the metrological performance of the Low Power Instrument Transformer, as reported in [5]. In [6] a system based on a synchronized current-comparator employing a digital sampler and transformers was implemented to calibrate voltage and currents of SAMUs at basic ranges of 120 V, 1 A and 5 A, using Wireshark software. A digitizer-based reference SAMU, which mirrors ± 10 V analog inputs into SV streams at sampling rates compliant with IEC 61869-9 and IEC 61850-9-2, is presented in [7]. The Keysight 3458A DMM was employed in [8], [9] for the calibration of electronic transformers, employing a coherent sampling algorithm synchronized via an external function generator.

While these studies have laid foundational work in SAMU calibration, they also reveal key limitations that restrict practical implementation and automation. All these approaches relied on external voltage dividers, shunts, or transformers to extend the range of the digitizers [4]–[9], increasing system complexity and hindering integration into automated workflows. The system in [6] used a hardware-intensive current comparator and manual SV capture, which, while precise, lacks scalability and integration. The digitizer-based SAMU in [7] demonstrated IEC-compliant SV generation; however, its use of fixed sampling frequencies constrained its flexibility and applicability in calibration tasks. Meanwhile, [8] and [9] employed commercial DMMs at a fixed frequency, yet did not quantify cross-range phase errors, support wide frequency range PTP/PPS-based synchronization, or eliminate reliance on external transducers. Moreover, although [9] acknowledged latency due to the operating system and hardware interfaces, no quantitative treatment was provided. These limitations highlight the need for a method that is automated, traceably accurate, and compatible with PTP/PPS-enabled equipment

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using widely available instrumentation—requirements that form the foundation of our proposed approach.

In this paper, a novel method is proposed for synchronizing PTP/PPS-enabled equipment with reference instruments that lack PTP or PPS support. This approach facilitates the use of widely available reference digitizers commonly employed in standards laboratories for calibrating PTP/PPS-synchronized equipment that streams the SVs. The proposed method utilizes a custom-developed software technique capable of operating within a non-deterministic operating system environment. Furthermore, a precise approach is introduced for quantifying the latency introduced by the measurement setup operating in such an environment.

The developed solution employs a multiharmonic least-squares fitting (MLSF) algorithm, previously implemented in the primary measurement standard for electrical power at the National Metrology Institute of Estonia (AS Metrosert) [10]. Combined with a reference multifunction instrument—such as the Fluke 8588A digital multimeter—capable of digitizing voltage and current signals over wide magnitude and frequency ranges without the need for external transducers, the system enables a highly accurate and fully automated calibration procedure while maintaining a minimal hardware footprint. To date, existing approaches have not addressed the full automation of the calibration process.

To validate the proposed concept, a comprehensive characterization of the 8588A digital multimeter's phase error across all voltage and current ranges was performed - work that, to our knowledge, has not been previously published.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the measurement setup used for calibrating the SAMU. Section III explains the software technique developed for synchronizing data from the SAMU and the DMM. Section IV describes the characterization of the DMM for use as a standalone reference in the automated calibration procedure, with phase error measurements detailed as part of an evolving procedure. Section V presents a discussion on the implications of phase error for SAMU calibration, along with the associated measurement uncertainties.

II. MEASUREMENT SETUP

The measurement setup, shown in Figure 1, consists of a Fluke 8588A DMM, a Vizimax SAMU-8 [11], a voltage and current source (U&I Source), and a master clock. Three types of synchronization signals referenced to the frequency standard are available: PPS, 10 MHz, and PTP.

The Fluke 8588A digital multimeter was selected for this study over single-range (± 10 V) digitizers due to its ability to digitize higher voltages (up to ± 1050 V) and currents (up to ± 30 A) with 18-bit resolution, high sampling rates up to 5 MHz, a low temperature coefficient, and excellent long-term stability [12]. Compared to another widely used reference multimeter in standards laboratories—the Keysight 3458A [13]—the Fluke 8588A offers several advantages, including higher digitizing rates, lower jitter, a broader current measurement range, and support for external 10 MHz synchronization. These

capabilities, along with two software-switchable inputs, enable a fully automated calibration procedure for stand-alone merging units. In digitizing mode, the DMM supports input values of up to 742 V and 21 A (RMS), accommodating the functionality of most SAMUs. If needed, these ranges can be easily extended by incorporating external transducers. A second DMM can also be added to the system for power measurements.

By default configuration, the DMM and the source are synchronized using a PPS signal. However, the method remains applicable with a free-running source, provided that a non-stationary output phase is acceptable. The SAMU can be synchronized using either a PPS signal or the PTP protocol.

A Fluke 5730A multifunction calibrator, along with a current amplifier, serves as the voltage and current source. The calibrator is synchronized to the common PPS signal using a function generator connected to the “phase lock-in” BNC connector on its rear panel, injecting a phase-locking signal at the test frequency. The function generator is ultimately aligned with the PPS signal. The absolute phase error of the source is not critical as it functions as a non-reference device. Additionally, the function generator and the DMM can be optionally clocked together using a common 10 MHz reference.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the measurement setup used for the calibration of the SAMU.

III. SOFTWARE TECHNIQUE

To enable synchronization of the Sampled Value streams, aligned by PTP/PPS signals, with data from a digital multimeter that lacks such support, a synchronization scheme is proposed (Figure 2), with an analytical formulation provided in (1) and (2). The proposed synchronization method was implemented in a software solution developed in the LabVIEW programming environment, employing the MLSF algorithm to enable non-coherent sampling at variable frequencies. Notably, the only requirement to initiate the DMM measurement sequence is the PPS signal.

A comparative study of algorithms commonly used for signal parameter estimation is presented in [14]. The implementation

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of the MLSF algorithm employed in this work was rigorously validated as part of the EMPIR Joint Research Project 15RPT04 TracePQM [15].

As shown in Figure 1, the SAMU streams the SVs, in compliance with IEC 61869-9 and IEC 61850-9-2 standards, over Ethernet to the network controller of a personal computer (PC) running Windows 11. The SAMU firmware supports several preconfigured combinations of sampling rates and the number of Application Service Data Units (noASDU), with a maximum sampling rate of 14,400 samples per second and noASDU = 8 [11].

When a rising edge of the PPS signal reaches the BNC input of the DMM in its waiting-for-trigger state, the DMM begins sampling the input for N periods at the selected sampling frequency. Initially, the data is stored in volatile memory before being transferred to the PC via the National Instruments GPIB-USB-HS+ controller. The impact of sampling frequency on measurement results is discussed in more detail in Section IV.

To ensure proper synchronization of the instruments, the sequence begins by setting the DMM into the waiting-for-trigger state, following the Idle state, as shown in the synchronization diagram in Figure 2. Immediately afterward, the program starts capturing Ethernet frames from the SAMU. The number of frames captured is configured to include 1 second of data plus the duration of N periods, $t(N_{period})$, and the execution latency, t_l , ensuring that N periods are acquired even in the worst-case scenario—when the measurement sequence starts just after the PPS rising edge (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Synchronization diagram of the SV stream with measurement data from the DMM.

The number of frames N_{frames} to capture is calculated as follows:

$$N_{frames} = \frac{f_{sampling}}{noASDU} \left(1 + \frac{N_{period}}{f_o(1-t_l f_o)} \right), \quad (1)$$

where

$f_{sampling}$ – sampling frequency of the SAMU,

N_{period} – number of periods to process,

f_o – operating frequency,

t_l – duration of the execution latency.

Although the DMM 8588A is optimized for rapid data transfer, a GPIB command execution in a non-deterministic operating system can introduce latencies of a few milliseconds,

referred to as the execution latency t_l in Figure 2. If the PPS rising edge arrives during this latency period, it can cause a 1-second time shift between the DMM and the SAMU. To mitigate this, measurement sequences in which the Sample Counter (smpCnt) at the start of the capture falls within the execution latency preceding the PPS rising edge are disregarded. The software handles such a measurement sequence as an exception (Figure 3). The highest allowed smpCnt_{high} at the start of the capture, which is the first condition in the data flow diagram, is determined as follows:

$$smpCnt_{high} = \lceil f_{sampling}(1 - t_l) \rceil. \quad (2)$$

The execution latency can be estimated using the measurement setup shown in Figure 1 by setting t_l to 0 and measuring the time interval between the PPS rising edge and the square wave signal at the TRIG OUT BNC connector of the DMM. The Trigger Out Reading Event is configured to Aperture Open, where the falling edge indicates the start of the integration period.

Under normal operating conditions, this time interval is approximately 130 ns, corresponding to the delay introduced by the internal circuitry of the DMM. If the PPS rising edge occurs within the latency period, the time interval meter registers a one-second time shift in addition to the internal circuitry delay. By simultaneously recording the smpCnt value at the start of the capture and using (2), the latency time can be determined.

For our measurement setup, which performed overnight measurements, the execution latency remained below 8 ms. According to (2), for a sampling frequency of 12800 samples per second, this implies that measurement sequences with the smpCnt at the start of the capture in the range from 12697 to 12800 are ignored.

Instead of relying on software conditioning for the execution latency, the time interval meter can be permanently integrated into the measurement setup to enhance synchronization control.

The second scenario in which the measurement data is skipped involves missed samples in the SV stream, which can be detected by identifying discontinuities in the smpCnt values. Along with exceptions caused by latency-related delays, both scenarios are classified as “Exceptions” in the data flow diagram of the developed software (see Figure 3).

If no exceptions occur, the software extracts sampled data from the SV stream for voltage and current channels, starting from smpCnt = 0, for processing. The signal parameters obtained from both the SV stream and the DMM are estimated using the MLSF algorithm. To optimize evaluation time, up to four voltage or current signals can be processed simultaneously. This computation takes less than 1 second on an Intel Core i5-1335U processor for three periods of analyzed data—the minimum required to ensure algorithm accuracy without compromising computational precision

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Fig. 3. Data flow diagram of the developed software.

IV. DMM CHARACTERIZATION

A. Magnitude

To utilize voltage and current digitizing functions of the DMM for calibrating synchronized signals received via SV streams, its inputs must be characterized for magnitude and absolute phase errors. Calibration of voltage ranges in terms of magnitude from 100 mV to 1000 V and current ranges from 1 mA to 10 A follows a standard procedure using either a characterized multifunction calibrator or a Fluke 792A AC-DC transfer standard and a set of cage-type AC-DC current shunts.

In the voltage calibration, the DMM and the reference standard are connected in parallel. In the current measurements, the DMM and the reference shunt are connected in series, where the output of the shunt is measured either by the second DMM or by the AC-DC transfer standard. The DMM under test is set to External Guard with the Lo and Guard terminals connected to the Hi output of the current source. Under standard conditions, a sampling frequency of 25 kHz is employed in power quality tests due to the calibration procedure used to evaluate the frequency response of the reference digitizers. In this procedure, the input frequency is varied from 50 Hz up to 2.5 kHz (corresponding to the 50th harmonic), while the sampling frequency remains fixed at 25 kHz and the aperture is set to 0.

B. Phase

The absolute phase error of the DMM is determined as follows: First, the DAC phase offset is characterized, as described in [16], to calibrate the 1 V range of the DMM. A step-up/down procedure is then performed using two Fluke 8588A DMMs and a set of precision phase-compensated, guarded resistive voltage dividers (RVD) [17] with the voltage coefficients (VCs) determined as described in [18]. The set of nine RVDs used in this study was originally designed for voltage scaling up to 1 kV within the reference standard for electrical power. Each RVD consists of a chain of metal foil

resistors with matched temperature coefficients, resulting in exceptionally low overall temperature dependence. The RVDs exhibit excellent long-term stability, and their frequency response has been characterized up to 10 kHz. These RVDs were thoroughly investigated for ratio measurement techniques as part of the EMPIR Joint Research Project 17RPT03 DIG-AC [19], [20].

The block diagram of the step-up procedure for characterization of the 10 V range is shown in Figure 4. This process calibrates voltage ranges from 100 mV to 1000 V, with both DMMs synchronized via the PPS signal. The results presented in Figure 5 for the range of 1 V to 700 V were obtained using a step-up procedure involving 18 measurements and 9 RVDs, whereas the range from 1 V to 100 mV was characterized using a step-down procedure with 4 measurements and 2 RVDs. At 50 Hz, the phase errors for all ranges, with the digitize filter bandwidth set to OFF, remain within 0.3 μ s at the measurement uncertainties ($k = 2$) less than 0.3 μ s (see Figure 5).

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the step-up procedure for calibration of the 10 V range (10VR) of the DMM.

Fig. 5. Phase error of the DMM over the voltage measurement ranges with the error bars denoting the measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$). The legend indicates the voltage ranges.

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Fig. 6. Phase error of the DMM over the current measurement ranges with the error bars denoting the measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$). The legend indicates the current ranges.

For phase characterization of the current ranges, two DMMs measure the same current: the device under test (DUT) directly at its current input and the reference meter measuring the voltage at the output of a cage-type shunt. A set of eleven precision current shunts, with 1-2-5 nominal values covering the range from 1 mA to 10 A with time constants traceable using techniques described in [21]–[23], was employed to characterize the phase error of the DMM across its current measurement ranges. The phase errors of the current digitizing input are within $1.5 \mu\text{s}$ for ranges from 1 mA to 10 A (see Figure 5). The measurement uncertainties ($k = 2$) are less than $0.4 \mu\text{s}$.

C. Sampling frequency and aperture time

Characterizing the DMM at a single sampling frequency and applying it for SAMU calibration at different sampling rates (ranging from 4000 to 14400 samples per second) is a practical approach. To validate this, the effect of the sampling frequency on phase error measurements was studied. Two DMMs measured the same voltage signal: the first operating at a fixed sampling frequency of 25 kHz, while the second varied between 4 kHz and 25 kHz. The measurement results (see Figure 6) remained within 10 ns, which is effectively within the 8588A's jitter specification [12].

A similar experiment was conducted for the aperture time, with the sampling frequency fixed at 25 kHz and the aperture varied from 0 ns to $1 \mu\text{s}$ on one DMM. The phase error of the DMM under test was approximately half the size of the aperture time. This is likely due to the averaging algorithm of the 8588A for apertures greater than 0 ns [24].

V. UNCERTAINTY CONSIDERATIONS

A. Magnitude Uncertainty

Uncertainty estimates in magnitude calibration, including major components due to the reference AC-DC standard and AC shunts, short—and long-term stability of the studied DMM, and environmental conditions, are within a few thousandths of a percent. This ensures a Test Uncertainty Ratio (TUR) above 5:1, trending to 10:1 for the magnitude performance evaluation of Class 0.05 SAMUs, as outlined in [3].

Fig. 7. Phase deviation at different sampling frequencies of the DMM with the error bars denoting the standard deviation.

Care should be taken regarding the long-term stability of the higher current ranges of the Fluke 8588A, which are specified with more relaxed tolerances. However, for the two DMMs used in this study, the calibration history demonstrates performance exceeding the specified limits by approximately an order of magnitude over a one-year calibration interval.

B. Phase Error Uncertainty

Since accurate alignment with Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) is not critical for relative phase error measurements, the primary concern is the jitter of the reference PPS signal, which is less than 1 ns. This signal is derived from a GPS-disciplined frequency standard and distributed through an 8-channel system.

The phase error of the DMM on its 1 V range, with an applied voltage of 1 V at 50 Hz, was calibrated using the method described in [16], yielding a result of (129 ± 50) ns. The DMM's jitter, specified to be below 10 ns, was confirmed during this study.

For the resistive voltage dividers, voltage coefficients relevant to the scaling procedure were determined in accordance with [18]. The largest contribution due to the VC at 50 Hz was observed for the 700:1 RVD, amounting to (-14 ± 17) ns, while for the remaining RVDs it typically remained within (-5 ± 5) ns.

The uncertainty associated with the time constants of the shunts used in this study was below 11 ns at 50 Hz, with the highest measured time constant of -44 ns corresponding to the 1 mA shunt. The relatively larger uncertainties at the beginning of each range in Figure 6 are primarily dominated by the Type A uncertainty associated with the DMM.

In practical applications, for the phase error of the most accurate 0.05 Class SAMUs, with a basic tolerance of $2.3 \mu\text{s}$ at 50 Hz [3], the TUR exceeds 6:1 at all measurement points, indicating that the measurement system can reliably determine whether the DUT is within or outside its specified limits. The dominant uncertainty component, typically due to DMM calibration, is below $0.2 \mu\text{s}$ (standard uncertainty, $k = 1$), while the highest Type A uncertainty, originating from the DUT, is $0.17 \mu\text{s}$.

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C. Impact of Phase Error on SAMU Calibration

The phase error results presented in Figures 5 and 6 demonstrate the high-resolution capability of the measurement system across broad voltage and current ranges, and have important implications for SAMU calibration in the context of IEC 61869-13. Even small phase deviations can propagate through the digital measurement chain and adversely affect critical power system functions. These phase errors, if not adequately characterized and corrected during SAMU calibration, can compromise the ability of the device to meet the standard's required accuracy class. By incorporating these corrections into the SAMU calibration workflow, the total measurement uncertainty is significantly reduced, supporting reliable performance in real-world grid applications where high accuracy and time synchronization are essential.

Experimental validation of the DMM demonstrates that the developed method achieves accuracy for calibration of the SAMU Class 0.05 in compliance with the standard IEC 61869-13 significantly lowering hardware costs and setup complexity.

VI. CONCLUSION

A new method is proposed for synchronizing SV streams generated by PTP/PPS-synchronized equipment—such as SAMUs—with measurement data from reference multimeters commonly used in calibration laboratories, which typically lack PTP/PPS support. The developed software technique operates in a non-deterministic environment, where the latency of the measurement setup influences synchronization fidelity. To address this, a novel approach is introduced for the quantitative estimation of this latency.

A multiharmonic least-squares fitting algorithm was implemented to enable non-coherent sampling with minimal hardware synchronization requirements, relying only on a PPS trigger for DMM-based digitization. The Fluke 8588A multimeter was selected due to its superior digitizing capabilities, low jitter, extended voltage and current ranges, and flexibility for automated calibration workflows.

The system was characterized using a set of precision voltage dividers and current shunts with time constants traceable through established techniques. The step-up and step-down procedures enabled accurate voltage scaling across wide ranges while maintaining low phase error uncertainties. Notably, the phase error introduced by the DMM and associated components was quantified in the nanosecond domain, ensuring the calibration setup supports the high accuracy and timing requirements of IEC 61869-13.

The practical implications of these results were discussed in the context of real-world grid applications, where even small phase deviations can significantly affect protection schemes and power quality monitoring. The proposed approach allows for traceable, low-uncertainty SAMU calibration, thus enhancing the reliability of time-synchronized measurements in digital substations.

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